

Multi-Beam Antenna for Ka-band CubeSat Connectivity Using 3-D Printed Lens and Antenna Array

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Abstract—In this paper, the design of a passive multi-beam lens antenna is proposed for the CubeSat space communication system as an alternative application of a 2-D microstrip antenna array that has originally been designed for a 39 GHz 5G MU-MIMO system. The half-ellipsoid lens is 3-D printed using stereolithography (SLA) technology. The antenna prototype is capable of selecting the main beam between 16 different directions with a gain ranging from 14 to 16 dBi and a half-power beamwidth of 14° to 18°. The measurements carried out in an anechoic chamber show good agreement with numerical simulations. The presented prototype shows that by employing 3-D printing technologies existing antennas can be easily and inexpensively converted to switched-beam or multi-beam solutions.

Index Terms—reconfigurable antennas, switched-beam antennas, passive multi-beam antennas, additive manufacturing, 3D printing, millimeter-wave antenna, fifth-generation (5G) communication, Internet-of-Things, CubeSat

I. INTRODUCTION

DURING recent years, the exploitation of space in the low Earth orbit (LEO) has grown rapidly, mainly through a large number of small satellites [1], [2]. These satellites require reliable and high-throughput inter-satellite and ground-to-satellite communication networks. To achieve this, the Internet of Space Things (IoST) system has been proposed as a space extension of the Internet of Things (IoT) paradigm. The main components of IoST networks are ground stations, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), and small satellites called CubeSats [1]–[3] which are used to create satellite constellations.

The wireless communication in the IoST can be realized in a wide spectrum, ranging from L-band (1–2 GHz), through X-band (8–12 GHz), up to Ka-band (26.5–40 GHz) [1]. The key components of wireless networks are antennas which should provide the best possible performance preserving the smallest possible dimensions as the available space inside satellites is limited [4]–[6]. In the millimeter-wave bands, high-gain antennas are often needed. Usually requiring a large aperture,

This paper is a result of the BEYOND5 (www.beyond5.eu) project which has received funding from the ECSEL Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 876124. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and France, Germany, Turkey, Sweden, Belgium, Poland, Netherland, Israel, Switzerland, Romania. The document reflects only the authors' view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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they are difficult or impossible to realize within the CubeSats' size constraints. Alternatively, a low-gain antenna element can be coupled with a dielectric lens thus increasing the gain without an excessive growth of the physical aperture [11]. Adding a lens can also turn an antenna comprising a set of separately fed radiators into a multi-beam or switched-beam antenna. Such antennas provide beam diversity that is often preferred in various IoST scenarios to improve connectivity. In the context of CubeSats, passive multi-beam antennas [7] and single-input reconfigurable antennas, such as switched-beam antennas [8]–[10], are particularly interesting. Although they usually provide less flexibility than digital beamforming solutions, they have lower complexity and energy consumption.

In the literature, several examples of lens-based switched-beam and multi-beam antennas can be found [11]–[21]. The typical design consists of an antenna (or an array of planarly distributed antennas) placed behind a dielectric lens [11]–[18]. In [11], the general lens-based multi-beam antenna and its implementation were presented. The beam direction can be deflected by changing the active radiating microstrip patch. Similar designs with added switched feeding networks are investigated in [12], [13]. Designs in [19]–[21] show a similar approach to realizing switched-beam or multi-beam antennas, where multiple antenna radiators are placed around a single lens. Each radiator is aligned with one of the lens' axes of symmetry and the beams are focused in those directions. This approach provides wider scanning angles than by placing radiators in one plane. A disadvantage of these solutions is that they are usually very large compared to the wavelength and would be difficult to fit into a small satellite.

The dielectric lens used in the switched-beam antenna designs can have ellipsoidal [11], [18], hemispherical [12]–[14], circular [19], [21], or even flat shapes [15]–[17]. Regardless of the shape, which can be chosen arbitrarily, the lens is usually optimized to maximize the gain or angular coverage of aggregated antenna beams. The antenna lenses can be quickly and affordably manufactured in 3-D printing technology, such as SLA (stereolithography) or FDM (fuse deposition modeling) [14], [17], [22]–[26].

In this letter, we propose a new approach different from the state-of-the-art designs which optimize the system of radiators together with the lens to create an integrated switched-beam or multi-beam antenna. In our work, an existing antenna array, designed, optimized, and fabricated for a stand-alone

Fig. 1. Design of a multi-port dual-polarized antenna array with a holder - overall top view (left) and a single antenna element with solder pads for SMPS connectors (right). Lens outline (diameter D_L) is in light blue.

application in 5G MU-MIMO systems, is adapted to create a passive multi-beam antenna intended for space applications by coupling it with a 3-D printed dielectric lens. Alternatively, the proposed antenna can be used for beam switching operation if an appropriate switching circuit is added. In the paper we describe the employed antenna array, present the design and fabrication of the lens, and discuss measurement results comparing them with the numerical simulations. The presented modular approach, which is the novelty of this work, could be employed for any multi-port planar antenna array designed for another mode of operation, like digital or analog beamforming, particularly intended for inter-satellite communication. It is especially beneficial in CubeSats, where lightweight printed lenses can be inexpensively customized to match particular mission communication scenarios without changing the radiator array and feeding network.

II. ANTENNA DESIGN

The proposed antenna design utilizes a previously realized and measured multi-port linearly dual-polarized microstrip array [27], presented in Fig. 1. In this work, only the horizontal polarization is investigated. The array is formed by 16 elements, each consisting of a radiating patch and feeding network. The microstrip patches are placed with a spacing R between their centers, which is constrained by connector size and a diameter of a single patch. The R value was chosen as $0.75 \lambda_0$, where λ_0 is free space wavelength at the resonant frequency (39 GHz). The design uses a two-layered substrate with patches on the top layer (CuClad217 substrate with 0.254 mm thickness) and a feeding network on the bottom layer (RT/duroid 5880 substrate with 0.127 mm thickness).

A circular microstrip patch of diameter D is chosen as a radiating element due to its symmetry required for dual-polarized operation [28], [29]. The patch, as shown in Fig. 1, is fed through two orthogonal C-shaped slots in the ground plane. The slots are defined by three parameters: width W_s , lengths

TABLE I
DIMENSIONS OF THE ANTENNA, IN MM

D	W_s	L_{s1}	L_{s2}	S_1	S_2
2.6	0.2	0.974	0.535	0.9	0.45
L_1	R	D_L	H_L	S_L	A_L
2.15	5.77	37.0	16.5	5.5	30.96

Fig. 2. Side view of the antenna array with the lens. The array PCB and SMPS connectors are drawn as they are hidden within the holder.

L_{s1} , L_{s2} and are placed with a distance S_1 from the patch center. The antenna is fed through miniature SMPS connectors soldered to feeding microstrip lines on the bottom layer. They have a length of L_1 and are placed with an offset of S_2 from the patch center. The numerical values of the dimensions are presented in Tab. I.

The array was adapted to a design of multi-beam antenna by adding a homogeneous all-dielectric half-ellipsoid shaped lens, providing both beam deflection and gain enhancement. 2-D beam selection of the antenna is realized by exciting ports of single patches selectively. This allows for an alternative beam-switching operation by using an optional switching circuit connected to the SMPS ports. Deflection of 16 separate beams is possible due to the diversity of patch positions

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3. Simulated gain at 39 GHz for all possible beams: a) half-power gain contours, b) aggregated gain heat map (dBi).

relative to the axis of the lens. A side view of the antenna with the array PCB and SMPS connectors is presented in Fig. 2.

The lens was optimized by changing its dimensions (D_L , H_L , S_L) for fixed $\epsilon_r = 2.66$. The goal consisted of three criteria regarding beam shaping: scan loss lower than 3 dB, 360° coverage in the horizontal plane (variable ϕ) for a given θ , and beams wide enough to provide continuous coverage with gain variation less than 6 dB. Dimensions of the designed lens are as follows: diameter $D_L = 37$ mm, which corresponds to $4.8\lambda_0$ at 39 GHz, height $H_L = 16.5$ mm and the spacing $S_L = 5.5$ mm. The air gap prevents severe degradation of the antenna matching and has an impact on the main beam direction. Using a lens with larger diameter increases antenna gain, but at the same time limits beam deflection angle. The maximum antenna radiator to lens center offset is 8.7 mm in both array axes.

The gain plots of all 16 beams obtained from simulations performed using Altair Feko 2021.2 software are shown in Fig. 3a and Fig. 3b. Fig. 3a shows half-power gain coverage relative to the maximum gain for each beam. The beams are denoted by the symbols of corresponding excited patch radiators introduced in Fig. 4. An aggregated gain plot as a heat map with a maximum value equal to the common maximum gain of all beams $G_{max} = 16.9$ dBi (for beam V_{A3}) is in Fig. 3b. The maximum simulated gain of individual beams ranges from 14.3 dBi to G_{max} , while the maximum

Fig. 4. Antenna elements corresponding to the beams shown in Fig. 3a.

Fig. 5. Fabricated antenna a) array top view b) array bottom view c) array with lens mounted on a turntable in anechoic chamber.

gain of a single patch radiator is 7.4 dBi. The plot shows that the antenna provides continuous coverage in the whole 360° range for ϕ and $0^\circ - 33^\circ$ range for θ with the gain variation of mostly less than 5.2 dB. There are only a few very narrow spots where the gain falls from G_{max} by 7.5 dB. From this plot, one can also read the directions of the beams and choose the angular cross-sections for corresponding radiation pattern measurements. Simulated antenna efficiency ranges from 48% to 53% and SLL in maximum gain cross-section ranges from -19.2 to -14.3 dB.

III. FABRICATION AND MEASUREMENTS

The designed antenna array was manufactured in a standard multi-layer PCB technology and its top and bottom view with 3-D printed holder are presented in Fig. 5a and 5b, respectively. The lens was fabricated using 3-D printing SLA technology, which is more precise compared to simpler 3-D printing methods such as FDM. FormLabs High Temp resin with dielectric properties reported in [31] equal to $\epsilon_r = 2.66$ and $\tan\delta = 0.03$ was used as a dielectric material. Being durable and having a low density of $1.28 \frac{g}{cm^3}$, it is a competitive material to silicon glass used in [12] concerning the lens weight, which is relevant in space applications, particularly in CubeSats. The weight of the fabricated lens is 15.2 g. The fabricated prototype of the antenna is shown in Fig. 2. The

Fig. 6. Simulated and measured normalized radiation patterns (dB) at 39 GHz in vertical plane (θ) in cuts at fixed angles a) $\phi = 315^\circ$ b) $\phi = 290^\circ$ c) $\phi = 345^\circ$.

lens is mounted at a fixed distance from the array PCB using a 3-D printed spacer (a green structure in Fig. 2).

All measurements were conducted using a measurement setup consisting of an anechoic chamber, a R&S ZVA50 network analyzer, a transmitting antenna, and an antenna under test in receiving mode, held by a stand placed on a turntable. Radiation patterns in the elevation plane are measured in the range of θ from -80° to 80° with a resolution of 2° . Because the antenna array is uniform and symmetrical, only radiation patterns for a group of four representative radiating patches ($V_{D1} - V_{D4}$) were measured, while the rest can be approximated by mirroring. The vertical cuts were set individually for each beam at ϕ angles of their maximum gain: V_{D1} in $\phi = 315^\circ$, V_{D2} in $\phi = 345^\circ$, V_{D3} in $\phi = 290^\circ$ and V_{D4} in $\phi = 315^\circ$. Because of its broad beam, V_{D4} was also measured at $\phi = 290^\circ$ and 345° for comparison with V_{D1} and V_{D2} . Fig. 5c presents the prototype in the anechoic chamber

Fig. 7. Measured reflection coefficient of patches $V_{D1} - V_{D4}$ with and without the lens.

TABLE II
MEASURED PARAMETERS OF BEAMS V_{Dn}

beam symbol	bare patch	V_{D1}	V_{D2}	V_{D3}	V_{D4}
main lobe θ direction [$^\circ$]	0	40	30	26	14
HPBW [$^\circ$]	31.8	17.6	14.0	16.9	17.8
SLL [dB]	-14.6	-9.4	-10.6	-10.2	-19.2
gain [dBi]	6.5	14.7	15.8	15.1	14.5

with marked directions of rotation for θ and ϕ angles.

The measurement results for beams V_{Dn} are summarized in Table II. The simulated and measured normalized radiation patterns in the vertical cuts are compared in Fig. 6a – 6c, and it can be noticed that they agree very well. The main lobe direction for all excited patches differs at a maximum of 2° from simulation results. The most significant discrepancy is in sidelobe level (SLL), which in the worst-case increases from simulated -18 dB to measured -10.2 dB. The measured gain is equal to 6.5 dBi for the bare patch and in the range of $14.5 - 15.8$ dBi for single beams ($V_{D1} - V_{D4}$) with the lens. The 3 dB gain bandwidth is 12.3% . The average simulated dielectric loss in the lens is 2.3 dB at 39 GHz, which results in total simulated efficiency of 47% to 54% for the beams V_{D1} to V_{D4} . In effect, calculated directivity is 17.8 dBi to 18.4 dBi, which corresponds to aperture efficiency of 26.2% to 30.8% .

The measured values of the reflection coefficient for beams V_{Dn} are shown in Fig. 7. There is only a small deterioration of the reflection coefficient caused by the lens so no further matching improvement is required. The -10 dB matching bandwidth for the worst case (V_{D3}) is 38.3 GHz to 40 GHz.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we present a design and experimental verification of a millimeter-wave multi-beam lens antenna that directly adapts a separately designed multi-port patch array by adding a 3-D printed lens. The antenna produces separate beams in 16 different directions and can be extended to provide a switched-beam operation. One of the advantages of the designed lens is that no additional optimization of the array is required because the designed lens has a minor influence on the antenna matching. Due to its small physical aperture and weight, the antenna is suitable for the IoST applications, such as inter-satellite communication in CubeSat constellations. Another advantage of the proposed modular approach to designing lens-based multi-beam antennas is that they can be customized for specific missions by replacing only inexpensive printed lenses.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Financial support of these studies from Gdansk University of Technology by the DEC-3/2020/IDUB/III.4.3/Pu grant under the PLUTONIUM - 'Excellence Initiative - Research University' program is gratefully acknowledged.

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